

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B264
 Date: 01 Feb 2007
 Take Off: 07:55:20
 Landing: 10:25:58
 Flight Time: 2h30m38

Campaign: IASI

Operating Area: N Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
9	MARSS / FWVS	James Bowles	Met Office
10	SWS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
12	Experience Flight 1	Carolyn Cook	Cardiff University
13	Experience Flight 2	Darren Hayton	Cardiff University
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B264 Track 01-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b264
 Date: 01 Feb 2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: N Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
064947		Start-Up	-.05 kft	111	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
074044		INU	-.06 kft	111	To Navigate Mode
075520		T/O	0.50 kft	322	Cranfield
075958		ASPs	7.0 kft	037	Open
082103		Videos	15.0 kft	037	Start UFC & DFC
082213		Heimann	15.0 kft	036	Cal
084518	090407	Run 1	-.21 - -.18 kft	326	A - B,QNH1026, 100'
085658		Heimann	-.19 kft	327	Cal
090505	091335	Profile 1	-.23 - 8.0 kft	333	From 50' Too much cloud for IASI, abort Plan A
091544	094420	Profile 1	8.0 - 32.0 kft	177	For FWVS
094421	095641	Run 2	32.0 kft	198	For FWVS
095457		Videos	32.0 kft	237	End UFC & DFC
095507		Videos	32.0 kft	237	Start RFC
095718	101535	Profile 2	32.1 - 11.7 kft	186	End at 12k'
102558		Land	-.09 kft	358	Cranfield
103504		Shutdown	-.10 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W
103800		Videos			Stop Recording AFC

B264 Track 01-FEB-07

Sortie brief: METOP (IASI) overpass over ocean

Mission Scientist: Phil Brown

Flight B264

Aim: To measure infrared radiances and the state of the atmosphere for calibration /validation of IASI on METOP-A satellite.

Location: Over open ocean. The mission scientist will determine the area of operations so as to operate in clear skies.

Weather conditions: Completely cloud free conditions at all altitudes are highly desirable; small amounts of cloud in limited areas are acceptable.

Key instruments: ARIES; AVAPS (15 sondes to be launched); temperature and water vapour sensors; Core Chem, MARSS, SAWS hygrometer, FWVS.

Radiation instrument operators' special instructions:

ARIES: At high level mainly nadir, short view of zenith during one run.

At low level one or (preferably) two short views at nadir otherwise mainly zenith.

HEIMANN: Mission scientist should ensure Flight Manager performs short cal of Heimann during the 100ft run(s) (at start or end) but that this does NOT clash with the ARIES nadir views.

Fixed Points: The runs will be over fixed ground positions in clear sky conditions. This sortie is NOT directly under the sub-satellite track so orientation is not critical and should be decided to maximize clear conditions.

A = 54°50'N 3°30'E

B = 56°10'N 2°00'E

1. Take off, transit to operating area arriving at low level (45 mins)
2. Start straight and level run from A to B at lowest permitted altitude (25 mins)
3. Profile ascent from lowest permitted altitude to max altitude at 1000ft/min to finish at point B (45 mins) **Note** that once fuel has been burnt if extra height can be gained then profile up to new max altitude between straight and level runs.
4. Start run from B to A (15 mins)
5. Start run from A to B launching sonde at start of run then every 3 mins (15 mins)
6. Start run from B to A to coincide with **IASI overpass** 1037Z launching sonde at start of run then every 3 mins (15 mins)
7. Start run from A to B launching sonde at start of run then every 3 mins (15 mins)
8. Start run from B to A (15 mins)
9. Start of profile descent from max altitude to lowest permitted altitude @ 1000ft/min to finish at point A (35 mins)
10. Start straight and level run between A and B at lowest permitted altitude (25 mins)
11. Transit home (45 mins)
12. Land (Total sortie time 4:55)

Mission scientist Debrief

Flight No. B264

Phil Brown

1 Feb 2007

Planned as a flight to measure up- and down-welling radiances in clear air within the range of the IASI instrument on the METOP satellite. Examination of satellite images prior to flight suggested that the required cloud-free conditions would be difficult to obtain but just about possible.

Transit at 15000ft to central N.Sea (~55N 3E), suggested that required cloud free conditions may just be obtainable. Descent to 100ft for initial run sampling downwelling radiances and obtaining Heimann radiometer calibration data. During this run, patchy altostratus cloud was persistent and there was also persistent thin cirrus cloud. In view of the requirement for clear sky conditions, it was decided to **abandon** the primary sortie at this point. One profile ascent to 32000ft was conducted to provide test data for the FWVS.

General synoptic situation.

Anticyclone centred to the S of Ireland with a broad warm sector over the UK at midday. Warm front lying approximately Holland – Shetlands producing incomplete cloud clearance due to moist profile persisting through most of the troposphere..

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.264** Date **1/2/07** Name **P. Brown** Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0755	in				To cowfield. QNH 1028
/				Patches As & Ci to the N & E.	
/				Mist patches around on the grid.	
0806		15000	037	approaching the Wash. Patches As just below & extending ahead for a while.	
/				Masses of contrails on SE horizon.	
0814			"	Tracks looks roughly parallel to edge of As region. Definite clearance away on W of track but still wispy Ci.	
0829		"	"	Extensive layers As above & below at this stage. Seems free of low cloud below & also clearance to NW along proposed A-B track	
/				Indescent 1026 QNH.	
0840				on track A-B. Still As above but clearance ahead	
0845			328		
0845/8		100			Start R1
0859					Mostly clear of As above now but probably thin over of Ci This is thicker away to E
0904/7				End R1	
0905/5			50		Start P1
					sortie abandoned - not going to be suff. clear patches.
0913/35		8000			holding; turn reciprocal.
0914/21		32000			End P1 start R2 for 10 min
0916/34		32000			End R2 start P2 for F100

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B264 **T/O:** 075520
Date of flight: 1/2/07 **Land:** 102558

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B264
Date of Flight: 1/2/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer B264.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (B264.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B264.zip	Y	Size of B264.dat = 360294
6) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	Y	Blocks read = 59425
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B264.dat	Y	Blocks written = 59425
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B264_seadas.dat	Y	Bad reads = 0
WAVE> exit	Y	
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	Y	
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: B264	Y	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B264_seadas.dat	Y	
d) Comment string:	Y	
e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i>	Y	Start = 0
f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i>	Y	End = 240000
g) Read 2DC: Y	Y	Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y	Y	(vestigial error from tapes)
i) Secondary data: Y	Yy	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	Yy	Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC
k) cmd.str: Y	Y	files in PMSDATA?
l) Auto time correction: N	Y	Are they non-zero in size?
m) Full length secondary: N	y	
8) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	2D image display and printing
i). WAVE> imagedisplay	Y	Must be done from FLOODS itself.
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: B264	Y	
c) File generation no: 0	Y	
d) Time from IWC plot: N	Y	
e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP	Y	
f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i>	Y	
g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i>	Y	
h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images)	Y	Note any problems with images
ii). WAVE> auto_image	Y	Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: B264	Y	
c) Enter date: 20070201	Y	
d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i>	Y	Start = 0
e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i>	Y	End = 240000
f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10	Y	
iii). WAVE> exit to create files	Y	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_
iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC	Y	Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps
v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter	Y	Notes on this in instructions
vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = Vol flow rate =
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X =b Y = X+1 =c
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B264** Date **1/2/07** Operat or(s) **Jeff Brown** log page **1** of **3**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
0630						Switch on - modules a little slow to re-act but all ok.			
0654						SWS + USM taking 5-10 sec to toggle to Idle on selecting Dark. Toggle back instantly on selecting scene all.			
						"Video" circuit breaker not working.			
0757						Take off			
080521		10000	174°A	1000		Modules set for transit.	✓		
080610			174°A	1000		Horace data not available.		✓	
			174°A	1000					✓
081655		15000	174°A	750		Dark		✓	
081713		15000	174°A	750		Scene		✓	
082036		15000	174°A	750		Dark - over Sc5 (3/8)			✓
082103		15000	174°A	750		Scene			✓
082233		15000	174°A			Entered Ac			
082430		15000	174°A			Between Ac layers			
084030		8500	174°A			In cloud during descent.			
084530	R 1	100	174°A	1000		Dark (below Sc + Ac)			✓
084604	R 1	100	174°A	1000		Scene (vis 20km-10km)			✓
0857	R 1	100	6°F			SWS lead to Zenith (clear patch)			
090335	R 1	100	6°F	500		Scene			✓
090359	R 1	100	6°F	500		Dark			✓
090505	P 1 ↗	50	6°F			Start of profile ↗			
090612	P 1 ↗	1000	6°F	500		Dark all	✓		
090643	P 1 ↗	1000	6°F	350		Scene all			✓
091430		8000	6°F			Bombing during ↗ intercept			
0918		10000	6°F			Hazy below Ci Ac + (on trails above)			
0930		27000	6°F			Above T+8 Sc/Ac/A2			
		27000	6°F			2/8 Ci above.			
093914		30000	6°F	1000		Scene Dark all	✓		
		30000	6°F	350					✓
093957		30000	6°F	750		Dark Scene all			✓
0943	R2	32000	Various			Temp -50 - checked movement on SWS head - appears OK to move if a little stiff			
	R2	32000	Various						
	R2	32000	Various						
094940	R2	32000	6°F	400		Dark			✓
095050	R2	32000	6°F	400		Scene. Clear below over 2000.			✓
	R2	32000	6°F			2/8 Ci above.			
0958	P2 ↘	32000	6°F			Unable to get derived data from Horace. bar what was set up before T/O.			
100606	P2 ↘	22000	6°F	200		Dark			✓
100628	P2 ↘	22000	6°F	200		Scene			✓
1017						Head aft for landing.			

ARIES flight log

Flight: B264

page 1 of

Date: 01/FEB/67 Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A:2 B:2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
06 39 45	On Hugn	1x60	C80	C	71	31	Cdd. 1 120 2 240
06 40 22		"	H	C			Hol 3 360
07 55	TAKE OFF						
08 05 45	FL150?	1x60	C	C	71	31	
08 06 22	R1 "	"	H	C	71	31	TRANSIT = BREAKFAST.
08 45 15	100 ft.	1x60	C	C			0910
08 45 56		"	H	C	71	31	Flt cloud above
08 46 54	100 ft.	240x1	N	C	71	31	"
08 49		1x60	C	C			
08 49 37		"	H	C	71	31	"
08 50 18	100 ft.	240x1	N	C	71	30-5	
08 52 25		1x60	C	C	71	31	"
08 52 59		"	H	C	71	31	"
08 53 41	100 ft.	240x1	N	C	71	31	"
08 55 48		1x60	C	C			"
08 56 22		"	H	C			
08 57 08	100 ft.	240x1	Z	O	70	31	Patchy cloud above, thinning.
09 00 00		1x60	C	C			Typical - clear slot just as Z ends!
09 00 34		"	H	C	71	30	Contrail above
09 01 21	100 ft.	240x1	Z	O	70	31	Clear above (hint of Ci/contrail)
09 03 56		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09 04 22		"	H	C			Run cut short - unfavourable cloud cover.
09 05	P1 ↑						
09 44 22	R2	1x60	C	C	71	30	
09 44 56		"	H	C	70	31	
09 45 36		240x1	Z	O	70	31	Cut short - finger trouble!
09 46 59		120x1	N	C	71	31	Clear above? V then Ci?
09 48 11		1x60	C	C	71	31	
09 48 45		"	H	C	71	31	
09 49 23		180x1	Z	O	70	30	Shutter opened after view start!
09 51 55		1x60	C	C	71	30-5	
09 52 30		"	H	C	71	31	

Flight:

B264

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turbulence Check Press:
- Turbulence Diff Press:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3010A:
- INC:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Report Created 05/02/2007 11:37:13

Last Updated:

02/02/2007 10:41:24

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B264

Date: 01 February 2007

Instruments

1. TWC – u/s, not fitted
2. Nevzorov – LWC not responding to zero-cal. TWC okay.

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls
None

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 1/2/07

Flight No: B2684

Pre-Flighter: RP

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	N/A	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	✓	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	✓	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
8	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	✓	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	✓	GPS	Checked	
13	✓	INU	Align	
14	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	N/A	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	O3 + NOx only
16	N/A	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	N/A	FWVS	Set up	
18	✓	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	N/A	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	✓	GE	Balance checked	
23	✓	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	✓	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	✓	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	✓	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	N/A	CGPS	Set up	U/S
28	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
External Checks overleaf				▶

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> ✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	Not fitted
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B264:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
Cloud Physics In Flight	CORRUPT file on SID2 PC - no log available
FWVS	No log is ever taken for FWVS
AVAPS	No sondes dropped

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

- 1 x Upward Facing Cameras
- 1 x Downward Facing Cameras
- 1 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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New plot, same times

Flight B264 10:13:26

Heading 266 deg Speed 255 knots Height 14.0kft Press 593mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 0°0.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 2 deg

Temp -12.84C Dewpoint -14.75C

From 09:11:15 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 36804 secs All
CABIN PRESSURE 951.64 mb

New plot, same times

Flight B264 10:12:50

Heading 267 deg Speed 253 knots Height 14.7kft Press 577mb

Lat 52°24.0'N Long 0°0.0'E Wind 14 ms-1/ 0 deg

Temp -14.45C Dewpoint -15.8C

From 09:08:26 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	36768	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
—	DEW POINT	-15.81	deg C	<input type="radio"/>
—	DEW POINT (FLUORESCENCE WVS)	-17.36	deg C	<input type="radio"/>